
BLOGPOST 2

Preventing the Next Coordinated Drone Strike: How the EU's PRESERVE Project Helps Defend Against Swarm-Based Attacks

Recent high-profile incidents involving coordinated drone strikes targeting public spaces, infrastructure and other sensitive sites have captured international attention and marked a turning point in the operational use of unmanned aerial systems (UAS). Such tactics are no longer a proof-of-concept but a strategic attack vector that pose growing challenges to law enforcement, critical infrastructure operators and military forces. While the actors, regions, and motivations may differ, many of these incidents share consistent tactical characteristics rooted in saturation, autonomy, and the flexible use of drone technology.

In most cases, attackers deploy multiple drones simultaneously or in rapid succession to overwhelm detection and neutralisation systems. This saturation tactic is designed to exploit gaps in coverage and response time, making it difficult for conventional countermeasures to isolate and neutralize all incoming UASs effectively. These operations frequently rely on the use of pre-programmed autonomous flight paths, allowing drones to navigate without real-time remote control. This autonomy reduces vulnerability to signal jamming or interference.

Commonly, the drones are assembled from commercial off-the-shelf components, widely accessible and easily modified for various tactical needs. Payloads are often adapted to local contexts and may include explosives, flammable materials, or electronic warfare tools. Importantly, many attacks include redundant or wave-based strike patterns, where if the first group of drone is intercepted, a second group follows shortly after, either along the same route or using alternate trajectories.

The overall tactical approach is clear: **maximize effect through scale and autonomy**, while **minimizing cost, traceability, and risk to the attacker**. These operations are difficult to detect in advance, particularly when the drones display no active RF emissions, carry low radar signal design, and operate at low altitudes. In some reported cases, planners leveraged commercial-grade components and open-source navigation software, further lowering the technological barrier.

Looking Ahead: Coordinated multilayered C-UAS for a Coordinated Threat

To counter this challenge, Europe must develop detection and mitigation solutions aligned with these realities. The **PRESERVE** project, a Horizon Europe initiative (with Grant Agreement No. 101168392) addresses this by developing a tailored platform integrating online pre-attack intelligence, multimodal sensor fusion, real-time threat assessment, predictive modelling and adaptive response mechanisms to protect against hostile drone swarm attacks. Particularly, it covers:

- **Multi-sensor capabilities and data fusion** for detection and situational awareness, including the capacity to monitor multiple objects in parallel under diverse conditions.
- **Online scanning of digital ecosystems** to detect pre-attack indicators, giving the ability to anticipate and assess threats.
- **Behaviour analysis and trajectory prediction** to support threat assessment and recommendations for appropriate mitigation responses
- **Neutralisation capabilities**, combining different response layers that are proportionate, context-aware and aligned with European legal and ethical standards.
- **Scalable and networked system**, enabling deployment across diverse environments—urban and rural, national and cross-border—with coordination between sites and jurisdictions.

By targeting every layer of the attack chain—from digital planning to physical engagement—PRESERVE represents a forward-thinking, that will be validated operationally.

Article by Eduardo Villamor Medina Senior Project Manager at ETRA.